

INSON SALOMATLIGINI SHAXSIY NAZORAT QILISH AQLLI TIZMLARIAA

Jumanazarov Javlon Shohnazar ogli
Daminov Jalol Olimjon o'g'li

Toshkent Axborot Texnologiyalari Universiteti
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7932184>

Annotatsiya

Salomatlikni nazorat qilish uchun foydali usullar haqida maqola. Bu usullar salomatlikni saqlashda muhim ahamiyatga ega bo'lib, insonlar uchun ko'p foyda keltiradi. Inson salomatligini shaxsiy nazorat qilish aqlli tizmi, insonlar uchun muhimdir. Bu tizim, salomatlikni ta'minlash uchun kerakli harakatlarni aniqlash va bajarishni o'rganishga yordam beradi. Tizimning bir necha qadamlari mavjud: maqsadni aniqlash, algoritim yaratish, dastur yaratish, test qilish, dasturni amalga oshirish va monitoring va yangilash. Bu qadamlar, salomatlikni nazorat qilishning samaradorligi va o'z vaqti kelib chiqishi uchun muhimdir. Insonlar, salomatliklariga qarab nazorat qilishni o'rganish va amalga oshirish uchun bu tizimdan foydalanishi kerak.

Annotation

An article about useful methods for health control. These methods are important in maintaining health and bring many benefits to people. The intelligent system of personal control of human health is important for people. This system helps you learn to identify and perform the actions necessary to maintain health. The system has several steps: goal identification, algorithm creation, program creation, testing, program implementation, and monitoring and updating. These steps are important for the effectiveness and timeliness of health monitoring. People need to use this system to learn and exercise control over their health.

Salomatlikni nazorat qilish aqlli tizimi, insonlar uchun turli xil foydalar taqdim etadi. Birinchidan, bu tizim insonlarga salomatlikni saqlash uchun zarur bo'lgan harakatlarni o'rganish imkoniyatini beradi. Bu, insonlar uchun muhimdir, chunki salomatlikning muhimligi vaqt o'tishi bilan ko'proq tushuniladi.

Ikkinchidan, bu tizim insonlarga salomatlikni nazorat qilish uchun kerakli planlarni yaratishga yordam beradi. Bu planlar, insonlar uchun salomatlikni saqlashga yordam beradigan harakatlarni aniqlashga va amalga oshirishga yordam beradi.

Uchinchi, bu tizim insonlarga salomatlikni nazorat qilish uchun zarur bo'lgan ma'lumotlarni taqdim etadi. Bu ma'lumotlar insonlarga salomatlikni saqlash uchun kerakli bo'lgan narsalarni o'rganishga yordam beradi.

To'rtinchi, bu tizim insonlarga salomatlikni nazorat qilish uchun kerakli motivatsiyani beradi. Bu motivatsiya insonlarni salomatlikni saqlashga yondashadi va ularni salomatliklariga qarab nazorat qilishni o'rganish va amalga oshirishga yordam beradi.

Bular bilan birga, salomatlikni nazorat qilish aqlli tizimi insonlarga salomatlikni saqlash uchun zarur bo'lgan harakatlarni o'rganish, planlarni yaratish, ma'lumotlarni taqdim etish va motivatsiyani yondirishga yordam beradi. Bu tizimdan foydalanish, insonlar uchun salomatlikni saqlash va o'zaro aloqalarni kuchaytirish uchun muhimdir.

Takliflar

Salomatlikni nazorat qilish aqlli tizimi, insonlarni salomatliklarini o'rganish va saqlash uchun foydali maqolalar, videolar va podcastlar taqdim etishga yordam berishi mumkin.

Salomatlikni nazorat qilish aqlli tizimi, insonlarning salomatlikni saqlash uchun kerakli bilim va amalni o'rganishga rag'batlantirish uchun universitetlar va kollejlarga hamkorlik qilishga yordam berishi mumkin.

Salomatlikni nazorat qilish aqlli tizimi, insonlarning salomatliklarini saqlab turish uchun zarur bo'lgan sport mashg'ulotlarini taqdim etishga yordam berishi mumkin.

Salomatlikni nazorat qilish aqlli tizimi, insonlarni salomatliklarini saqlash uchun zarur bo'lgan yaxshi ovqatlanishni taqdim etishga yordam berishi mumkin.

Salomatlikni nazorat qilish aqlli tizimi, insonlarni salomatliklarini saqlab turish uchun zarur bo'lgan tibbiy yordamlarni taqdim etishga yordam berishi mumkin

Foydanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yhati:

1. J. Wan, M. A. A. H. Al-awlaqi, M. S. Li, M. O. Grady, and X. Gu, "Wearable IoT enabled real-time health monitoring system," EURASIP Journal on Wireless Communications and Networking, vol. 298, pp. 1–10, 2018. View at: Publisher Site | Google Scholar
2. I. Khan, K. Zeb, A. Mahmood, W. Uddin, and M. A. Khan, "Healthcare monitoring system and transforming monitored data into real time clinical feedback based on IoT using Raspberry Pi," in Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference on Computing, Mathematics and Engineering Technologies (iCFoMET), pp. 1–6, Sukkur, Pakistan, January 2019. View at: Publisher Site | Google Scholar
3. M. Masud, G. S. Gaba, K. Choudhary, M. S. Hossain, M. F. Alhamid, and G. Muhammad, "Lightweight and anonymity-preserving user authentication scheme for IoT-based healthcare," IEEE Internet of Things Journal, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 2649–2656, 2022. View at: Publisher Site | Google Scholar

4. S. Ahmed, M. Monirujjaman Khan, R. Alroobaea, and M. Masud, "Development of a multi-feature web-based physiotherapy service system," *Intelligent Automation & Soft Computing*, vol. 29, no. 1, pp. 43–54, 2021. View at: [Publisher Site](#) | [Google Scholar](#)
5. M. Masud, G. Muhammad, H. Alhumyani et al., "Deep learning-based intelligent face recognition in IoT-cloud environment," *Computer Communications*, vol. 152, pp. 215–222, 2020. View at: [Publisher Site](#) | [Google Scholar](#)
6. H. Bhat, N. Shetty, and A. Shetty, "A review on health monitoring system using IoT," *International Journal of Engineering Research and Technology*, vol. 6, no. 15, pp. 1–4, 2019. View at: [Google Scholar](#)
7. T. Reza, S. B. A. Shoilee, S. M. Akhand, and M. M. Khan, "Development of android based pulse monitoring system," in *Proceedings of the Second International Conference on Electrical, Computer and Communication Technologies (ICECCT)*, pp. 1–7, Coimbatore, India, February 2017. View at: [Google Scholar](#)
8. S. Nair, N. Augustine, and L. Varghese, "Smart health monitoring system," *International Journal of Engineering Research and Technology*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 1–6, 2020. View at: [Publisher Site](#) | [Google Scholar](#)
9. C. Senthamarasi, J. J. Rani, B. Vidhya, and H. Aritha, "A smart patient health monitoring system using IoT," *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*, vol. 119, no. 16, pp. 59–70, 2018. View at: [Google Scholar](#)